

NON-CONTACT HOLISTIC MEASUREMENT OF AEROSPACE FASTENER HOLES WITH RING LASER ADAPTIVE OPTICS

George N Bullen

Keywords: Non-Contact, Aerospace hole analysis, Ring laser, Automation

ABSTRACT

The introduction of composite materials onto air vehicles has complicated the traditional hole/countersink assessment criteria due its finished-part thickness variability; softer and dissimilar properties than the metallic substructure where it is mounted and attached; and the increased attention to other acceptance criteria such as fiber tear, fiber pull, and moisture propagation in the hole that degrades fastener capability. The addition of composite materials further complicates the assembly process by adding a boundary layer of liquid shim or sealant between the composite piece (usually a skin) and the substructure.

Current hole inspection systems are absent the ability to assess the interior condition of the composite hole such as fiber tear, damage to the liquid shim, and debris or burrs between the multiple stacks of dissimilar material.

This paper will describe, illustrate, and define new non-contact laser inspection methods for assessing the acceptability of countersinks and holes in aerospace parts made from composite materials. The diagnostic system(s) can satisfy the full range of hole and countersink criteria and provide an evaluation of the composite material and liquid shim condition simultaneously; while collecting data to populate a knowledge base to facilitate advanced analytics.

1 INTRODUCTION

“Everything must be made as simple as possible. But not simpler.”

— Albert Einstein “

Today more than ever, air vehicle manufacturers recognize that the collage of global supply chain manufacturing processes and gauges needs a common unifying medium to insure best-fit at final assembly.

The largest component and cost for manufacturing fit-up at assembly are the holes that bind and hold the airframe together. Mitigating variability and cost from a myriad of inspection instruments used for hole/countersink assessment and diagnostics would unify the global supply base. A global supply chain that uses a common gauge to identify, inspect, collect, and distribute critical hole/countersink data would facilitate a digital tapestry for best fit. During manufacture, optimality analysis from a single non-contact gauge would stream collected data along the digital tapestry using advanced analytics to optimize parts manufactured across the global supply chain. This would ensure work-pieces best fit when assembled.

A single non-contact common gauge and advanced analytics capability would unite today’s complex global supply chain and mitigate the variability inherent in current diverse manufacturing environments. A single non-contact gauge applied across the global supply chain would also address the increasingly recognized challenges of drilling/countersinking composites by providing fidelity and capabilities not present in current gauges. A single non-contact gauge that provides a complete diagnostic image of hole quality is needed today to make sure that air vehicles of today meet the demands of tomorrow. And that air vehicles of tomorrow have a common gauge to meet the composite challenge as increasing amounts of composites used for parts make their way onto the airframe.

As composites have increasingly made its way onto the airframe, manufacturers have recognized the limitations of existing gauges that were designed for metals. Stacks of composites over metal assemblies have frustrated attempts to apply automated fastening. While automated drilling and countersinking have, and continues to spread across the airframe assembly landscape, automated

fastening has been limited due to the inability of current inspection gauges and processes to provide the needed diagnostics to “approve” a hole for automated fastener installation. Figure 1 shows a delamination point cloud resulting from a non-contact laser scan. The delamination went undetected by currently-used conventional gauges. Further complicating the application of automated fastening to composite-incorporated assemblies is the requirement for its 100% hole-countersink inspection. Figure 2 shows a hole delamination caused by mismatch between the pilot and fastener holes undetected by conventional gauges but revealed by a non-contact ring laser derived point cloud.

Figure 1: Showing Countersink Delamination

Figure 2: Delamination-offset to pilot hole and stack “split” location.

Issues unique to assemblies incorporating composite materials such as fiber pull and tear, location and identification of burrs and debris between stacks of material require special consideration. Figure 2 also shows the precise “split” location between stacks of material. Because current gauges fail to provide all the necessary criteria for acceptability and “approval” for fastener installation, complex manual evaluation (eyes on) of holes and countersinks must be performed before the fastener installation process can be completed. In many cases the process of evaluation includes taking the pieces of the drilled assembly apart to manually inspect, de-burr, and repair identified “issues” prior to reassembly.

Therefore a critical component to unify two robust types of automation (drill/countersink and fastener installation) into a single seamless process without manual intervention is needed. The critical barrier to automated drill-and-fill lies in the interim process of validation and certification of holes and countersinks for fastener installation integrated into the single operating system.

2 NON-CONTACT RING LASER (NCRL) CAPABILITIES

Non-Contact Ring Lasers (NCRL) are the only three dimensional scanner that can be made to fit inside and provide non-contact measurement, diagnostics, and analytics of the holes created as part of the aerospace manufacturing and assembly process.

Technical advancements have enabled development of NCRL specifically for the aerospace industry that include optimized optics for aerospace hole sizes, a laser delivery system optimized to illuminate and image the materials used in the aerospace industry, aerospace hole measurement, diagnostics, and analytics software, a robust manufacturing and field calibration system, and a hole location system that makes the NCRL readily implementable on the manufacturing floor

NCRL's are capable of unparalleled accuracy for a number of measurements such as hole dimension, debris, damage, depth, and perpendicularity (D4+P). For example, hole diameter is measured within .0001". Debris and damage are imaged in real time with accurate identification of the impact of drilling artifacts such as excess liquid shim, resin in the hole, burrs, gaps, cracks, and excess dust. Depth or grip length is measured within 0.001" and perpendicularity within 0.001". Composite-specific measurements are also identifiable such as pre-destack analysis, micro-delamination, gaps, and fiber tear.

Diagnostics Capabilities provides real-time hole diagnostics such as determining whether a hole is within or without a specified tolerance for D4+P. Furthermore, the repeatability of the NCRL reduces human subjectivity in evaluating hole diagnostics allowing for consistency across inspectors and inspection locations.

The NCRL is capable of maintaining a database of all measurements and diagnostic results along with a complete image of the hole. This data warehousing allows for predictive analytics of tool life, hole forensics, feed-back through maintenance and repair operations, and long term knowledge based analytics for improved manufacturing tolerances and manufacturing processes. NCRL's are closed looped analytic solutions that allow the actual impact of its use to be quantified. Figure 3 shows tool-wear hole scaring/rifling in composites revealed from a NCRL scan that would be undetected by conventional gauges. The NCRL data could be used to determine tool changes to optimize part quality. The paper should be written following the format of this template. The file has to be translated into Portable Document Format (PDF) before submission.

Figure 3: Rifling from tool wear.

The NCRL is especially well suited for measurement, diagnostics, and analytics of holes in composite materials which add additional considerations to hole inspection. Composite materials have thickness variability, softer and dissimilar properties than the metallic substructure upon which the composite is mounted and attached, and additional issues such as micro-delamination, indications of the need for de-stack, and in-hole fiber tears. Composite materials also have a boundary layer of liquid shim between the composite and the substructure that can lead to excess debris in the hole. The NCRL is non-contact so that it is not affected by debris within the composite hole and optically images the hole allowing unique composite artifacts to be analyzed.

Speed and Repeatability Capabilities provides measurements and diagnostics in real time. Measurement, diagnostics, and analytics are available for each hole as it is scanned. NCRL's are also extremely repeatable. One of the key aspects to the NCRL repeatability is the machine vision and imaging capability does not require precision by the operator. The NCRL will repeatedly provide an accurate measurement of the hole as long it is not touching the hole wall. Therefore, there is reduced human subjectivity in operation, measurements, and diagnostics provided.

Multiple Hole Size Capabilities derived from NCRL's provide a one size fits all solution. A single probe is capable of measuring and providing diagnostics for holes ranging in size from 3/16" (4.8 mm) to 3/4" (19mm) without any modifications or change in parts between holes. As such, the NCRL can be used to inspect almost all air vehicle holes.

3 NON-CONTACT RING LASER (NCRL) CAPABILITIES

Optical Probe

A 3.2 mm Diameter Optical Probe is used. It is a self-actuating optical probe and laser delivery system to illuminate and image the interior of a drilled hole for precise and repeatable hole diagnostics. The laser delivery system is engineered to project a ring of light within the hole for imaging. The laser light is specifically tailored to radially illuminate and image both metal and composite materials, as well as metal-composite stacks of materials

The probe also includes a wide-angle low distortion lens structure. The lens structure focuses the direct reflection of the radial light delivered into the hole ring onto a camera inside the scanner. The images captured on the camera are used to image the interior of the hole.

The probe of the NCRL is self-actuated and therefore automatically moves into the hole without making contact with either the hole itself or debris within the hole. As such, the probe and the images created through it are not corrupted by contact with the hole or debris. This makes the probe especially useful in measurement and diagnostics of composite holes.

The probe has consistently measured holes to a depth of 1.550 inches of material and provides accurate and consistent data even when offset from the center of the hole. Figure 4 shows a notional probe and its operating architecture.

Figure 4: NCRL probe and operating architecture (Notional).

Figure 5 shows an actual NCRL probe assembly.

Figure 5: NCRL Probe Assembly

Machine Vision Software

An NCRL includes a machine vision software package for hole imaging and diagnostics. The machine vision software provides real time D4&P assessment, complete hole imaging, predictive tool life-cycle analysis, and long-term knowledge based analytics. The software identifies the primary reflection of the ring of illumination light with extreme precision, filters all secondary reflections, and uses the filtered image of the primary reflection to both identify a D4&P assessment and create a three dimensional representation of the interior of the hole. The software is able to identify from the three dimensional representation of the hole predictive tool wear and analytics of the hole previously thought to be impossible or cost prohibitive. For example, the software is capable of identification of micro-delamination in composite materials, burs, rifling, gaps, and many other anomalies of the interior of a hole that are currently either ignored or identified in a cumbersome and costly manner.

Hole Location Guidance System

NCRL's are easy to use and requires little training for the user. Automated NCRL's have a hole location guidance system that directs the software to precisely align the NCRL over or under the hole. The hole location guidance system has an alignment camera which provides a live video stream of the alignment of the NCRL and also projects cross-hairs upon the live video stream. An operator can also visually align the cross-hairs upon the center of the hole that needs to be inspected. The guidance system automatically actuates the probe, images the hole, and provides three second real time measurement and diagnostics of the hole.

Manufacturing and Field Calibration Methods

The NCRL design provides a quick and long lasting calibration. The calibration method establishes a fixed position of the delivered laser illumination with respect to the lens assembly of the probe. The calibration method is quick and may be performed in the field by any operator. Once calibrated, the NCRL maintains that calibration. NCRL's take a few minutes to calibrate and stays calibrated unless damaged. This long term calibration equates to over 100,000 holes to be measured and imaged. This allows the NCRL gauges to be a repeatable and continuous source of precise and accurate measurement and diagnostics.

Back End Solution

The NCRL uses a back end solution that is designed as an extensible, reliable platform, which provides an interface for a variety of data collection, diagnostic, and analytical applications to interface with the Aerospace industry ecosystem. NCRL systems at their most fundamental level, are designed to manage the workflow of hole inspection and measurement.

4 NCRL CONCERNS

Dust and Debris

Concern about dust and debris exists when optics and laser based inspection gauges replace touch-

and-feel gauges. The effects of dust and debris are perceived to be less pervasive and negatively influential to the accuracy of a gauge that physically touches the surface of the object it measures.

Hand drilling and especially automated drilling is a messy business when the material engaged has composites as a component. Lubricants such as BOELUBE™ are mist sprayed and mix with composite dust. Figure 6 shows the debris that can accumulate inside the auto-drill/countersink pressure foot after only a few holes have been drilled.

Figure 6: Inside a Pressure Foot showing the accumulation of composite dust bound together with BOELUBE™

The debris can defeat accuracy in touch-type probes and non-contact optical laser probes. NCRL probes use boot type covers over the probe assembly that protects the probe until it is seated within the pressure foot. Figure 7 shows (CAD image) a NCRL probe inside a pressure foot with the protective boot and cap compressed to allow scanning of a hole.

Figure 7: Protective boot compressed to allow probe to emerge to scan a hole.

The probe is further protected when it is inside the boot and boot-cover by positive air pressure.

The glass probes in NCRL applications are easily cleaned using the variety of readily available and used aerospace manufacturing cleaning agents/solvents such as denatured alcohol, isopropyl alcohol,

and methyl propyl ketone (MPK).

Robustness

Another concern is the robustness of the glass part of the probe assembly. The concerns primarily reside in two areas, breakage and vibration.

Breakage

In both automated and hand operation the glass portion of the probe assembly is contained within a protective body. The glass probe only emerges when the probe is aligned and positioned. Safety switches confirm a clear path before the probe can exit the protection of its housing. Figure 8 shows the probe contained and retracted into its housing.

Figure 8: Probe assembly containing the glass probe is retracted inside its protective boot, boot-cap, and housing.

If broken or damaged, the probe assembly has a 5 minute change-out with new types targeting one-minute replacement.

Figure 9 shows a rapid replacement probe in its protective storage box with cover removed.

Figure 9: Spare probe with storage box cover removed ready for installation.

Vibration

Vibration occurs during machine motion, Drill/countersink, and fastening operations. Current NCRL systems have demonstrated they can withstand significant jarring and vibration without degradation of accuracy or breakage.

Systems have been tested to forces of 10 g's at 10 Hz in the x, y, and z directions for 5 seconds per hole during the fastener installation cycle.

Comparative Accuracy

Accuracy is demonstrated in by comparing the accuracy of current measurement gauges with NCLR measurements. Figure 10 shows one comparison between standard measurement gauges/practices and a NCLR gauge. Note that the increments are in tenths of a thousandth of an inch and take place over 1.4 inches of depth. Observing the differences of one or two tenths of a thousandth of an inch results from several factors. Traditional touch probes compress slightly the material they measure. NCLR are non-contact and observe the materials dimensions and conditions in their pristine untouched condition.

Figure 10 Comparison between "hard" measurements and non-contact measurements.

Figure 11 shows a typical scan result from a NCLR probe. The hole size is defined on the left side of the chart with depth on the bottom. The artifact just past 1.4 inches is where the two pieces of material are joined (mated) together.

Figure 11: NCLR probe result of a hole.

5 APPLICATION EXAMPLES

Types of NCLR gauges come in two primary application configurations; automated and handheld.

Automated

Automated systems are integrated into drill/countersink systems; or integrated into automated drill/countersink systems with auto-fastening capability.

Figure 12 shows the operating architecture of the automated NCLR when integrated into and coordinated with a Siemens 840D controller.

Figure 12: Automated NCRL configuration

Figure 13 shows an automated NCRL system mounted in its test stand.

Figure 13: Automated system mounted in its test stand.

Handheld

The hand held system adds the ability for normalization to the surface before activation of the probe operation. The handheld computer replaces the controller as the data collection medium.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Air vehicles are the most complex machines made today. Their configuration types are manufactured in small simple shapes and extend to very large sizes with highly complex shapes. Each production line is uniquely tailored with tooling to accommodate the size, configuration, precision, and manufacturing processes to make the rate required to meet demand for the air vehicle type.

Air vehicle's components and parts are made to highly precise dimensional tolerances with little forgiveness for variability and fabricated from a variety of light weight, high strength materials. Families of parts are joined together at progressively larger subassemblies until a completed air vehicle is attained. The method for holding all the work-pieces and subassemblies in proper configuration until joined together is the assembly tooling.

The primary means used to join all components, parts, and subassemblies of air vehicles are fasteners. Fasteners are inserted into holes that are tightly dimensioned to provide a precise fit for the fastener. The holes may be countersunk or un-countersunk. Countersunk holes are made to insert a flush type fastener and most fasteners are countersunk. The countersunk holes are predominantly on the exposed surface of the airframe, wing, and control surfaces and used for fasteners to attach skins to the substructure of the air vehicle. They are made flush to facilitate airflow over the surface of the skins they hold tight to the supporting substructure. Depending on the size and complexity of the air vehicle, the airframe can contain as many as 7 million holes for fasteners. The hole-drilling and countersinking operation accounts for as much as 65% of the cost of an airframe; 80% of the defects; and 80% of lost time injuries at the assembly level for an airframe.

Holes are drilled and countersunk in air vehicles using three primary methods. They are automated, mechanized, or hand drilled. The largest percentage of holes drilled today are by hand, followed by mechanized, and then automated. While today's holes are mostly drilled by hand, the increased demand for quality, efficiency, and repeatability has driven more and more aerospace manufacturers to install automated drilling and countersinking on new lines or convert old lines from hand drilling to the automated method of drilling and countersinking holes. Advances in machine controllers, machines/robots, and end-effectors have incentivized the move to automation to replace cumbersome tooling and the variability of the hand process.

Fasteners are the primary means by which all structure and skins are held together. Therefore the fasteners are a significant contributor and critical to the structural strength and integrity of the air vehicle and its ability to satisfy its design purpose. The holes and countersinks for each fastener's fit and function are the critical component to facilitate optimum performance from each fastener. A single fastener failure can cause catastrophic failure in the assembly it holds together with other fasteners (e.g. the zipper effect). Since the fastener-follows-the-hole, every element of the hole and countersink is assessed and evaluated for its conformance to specification for the specific fastener it will accommodate.

Specified hole/countersink conformance is generally a combination of position and D4&P. D4&P represents evaluation of Dimension, Depth, Damage, Debris, and Perpendicularity. In aerospace vernacular, perpendicularity is referred to as "normality" or "normal to surface".

The number of tools to assess and validate hole/countersink conformance is complex due to the breadth, depth, size, rate requirement, and maturity of the various assembly lines globally producing air vehicles and their components. The definition of the breadth and depth of hole/countersink assessment instruments is complicated by specific instruments used to evaluate each element of the hole. A countersink depth and angle conformance evaluation may use one instrument and a dimensional hole evaluation another instrument, while yet another instrument is used to evaluate the overall depth of the hole (grip length). The air vehicle manufacturing base and the finished air vehicle maintenance, repair, and overhaul (MRO) industry is awash in the variety and complexity of the hole/countersink instruments used today. Some instrument manufacturers have attempted to combine many of the D4&P criteria into a single assessment instrument but with limited success. The instruments generally have been expensive, complicated to use, and do not incorporate all the D4&P criteria into a single instrument, until the advent of the Non-Contact Ring Laser (NCRL) gauge/scanners.

In addition, the devices currently used have limited or no ability to collect data to populate a knowledge base for analytical assessment and evaluation to improve fit-up at assembly. When applied to automated systems, today's hole/countersink diagnostic instruments offer limited dimensional evaluation, do not provide simultaneous one-shot drill/countersink and hole/countersink evaluation, or hole/countersink predictive analytics. The NCRL can provide all of these capabilities in a single solution.

The introduction of composite materials onto air vehicles has complicated the traditional

hole/countersink assessment criteria due its finished-part thickness variability; softer and dissimilar properties than the metallic substructure where it is mounted and attached; and the increased attention to other acceptance criteria such as fiber tear in the hole. The addition of composite materials further complicates the assembly process by adding a boundary layer of liquid shim between the composite piece (usually a skin) and the substructure. The liquid shim material is extremely brittle when cured adding a drill routine that must accommodate drilling through dissimilar stacks of material concluding with “pulling” a metallic chip through a softer composite hole. Manufacturers are left with the inefficient manufacturing process of “de-stack” because mechanics cannot assess the interior condition of the composite hole such as fiber tear, damage to the liquid shim, and debris or burrs between the multiple stacks of dissimilar material. In the “de-stack” process, the manufacturer must remove the composite skin after drilling to evaluate the effects of drilling through the various stacks of dissimilar material. This step assures that the parts fit-up without interference from burrs and debris or that the drilling operation has not chipped, cracked, or otherwise damaged the liquid shim.

The requirement and opportunity for a device that can satisfy the full range of D4&P criteria and provide a full evaluation of the composite material and liquid shim condition simultaneously; while collecting data to populate a knowledge base to facilitate advanced analytics would provide a new disruptive technology to air vehicle manufacturers.

NCRL is an emerging disruptive hole/countersink technology that provides all the functionality of the multitude of gauges currently required for D4&P. It provides the added functionality for composite/liquid shim quality conformance assessment in-the-hole, eliminating the need for de-stack. The single operation provides a non- intrusive and non-contact holistic assessment of the complete hole/countersink while populating a knowledge base for future analytics to enhance best fit at assembly and variability reduction.

The NCRL solution can be utilized on assembly in the hand held model or integrated into the automated or mechanized end effector with the automated NCRL solutions. When incorporated into the automated drilling system, the design operates simultaneously with the drill/countersink operation to maximize utility and output of the valuable automated drilling system. Added functionality in the automated NCRL is its ability to predict hole degradation and tool wear for tool bit replacement to optimize hole quality and drill-bit life.

The functionality of the NCRL gauge can reduce the quantity of drill-tools (drill templates and drill bonnets) and their calibration, certification, and maintenance time by inspection of the bushings in the drill-tools in place without taking them off-line to their master models.

Global MRO and depot repair facilities enhance their ability to service and repair air vehicles that are composed of increasing amounts of composite parts. Repair of composite parts require a higher level of skill and fidelity than their metallic counterparts. The holistic diagnostic capability of the NCRL and its ability to capture data means that information can be sent back to the OEM or central repair and maintenance depot for evaluation and best recommendation for repair. Information can be collected in a knowledge base to determine recurrent repairs for forensic evaluation and corrective engineering of parts to enhance performance.

In summary, the NCRL is a disruptive technology for hole/countersink evaluation to meet all D4&P assessment, while adding material evaluation criteria, and advanced analytics in a single non-invasive 3 second operation. This functionality replaces the array of disparate instruments populating the air vehicle manufacturing and operations environment.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to acknowledge the engineers and scientists at United Sciences; specifically Karol Hatzilias and Harris Bergman.

REFERENCES

All data contained in this paper is derived from original research and development by United Sciences and the author.